

Analysis of Lean Critical Success Factors and Performance Measures of Lean Manufacturing using CB-SEM

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Abstract— identifying the critical success factor is crucial for successful management. Therefore, researchers who have studied the success of Lean in the past have unified all success paths and used them in the same way for all industries, and the implementation of Lean has failed. This study analyses the link between critical lean success factors and performance measures of lean in the industry organizational improvement. This study used a survey-based methodology. A total of 240 surveys were distributed and received feedback from 220 respondents, which demonstrates that the rate of responses was 91.6%. Exploratory and confirmatory factor analysis was used to check the reliability and validity of factor loading. Analysis of moment structures was used to examine the structural equation modelling relationship and hypotheses testing in the research model. The results confirmed that those critical success factors, such as financial capability and top management commitment have a significant positive impact on the performance measure of lean manufacturing. The standardized regression coefficient obtained was 0.37 and 0.31 with a level of confidence of $P < 0.001$, respectively. The policymakers, academic institutions, and other stakeholders who support the industry provide the necessary training and resources to promote the use of lean manufacturing concepts to increase its competitiveness and organizational performance. The study's findings can be used to increase the contribution of lean manufacturing to increase the productivity of the industry which impacts the country's economic development.

Keywords— AMOS, Confirmatory Factor Analysis, Covariance-based Structural Equation Modelling, Exploratory Factor Analysis, Lean Manufacturing

I. INTRODUCTION

In light of global challenges and intense competition manufacturing industries and organizations must enhance their capability to effectively implement the lean manufacturing concept [1]. The lean manufacturing concept is a method for continuous improvement. Its goals are to eliminate non-value activities and waste in manufacturing processes, reduce costs, and provide faster service with less human effort, time, and equipment by utilizing tools and techniques to achieve these goals [2]. However, with the increasing customer demand, products are rarely completed on time and within budget creating significant challenges for manufacturing companies. Thus, lean manufacturing is one of these concepts that attract the interest of both researchers and practitioners who have recently developed a lean implementation model to address these challenges. Over the last three decades, lean methods have grown substantially, and their principles and methodologies have been widely disseminated and adopted in both industrial and service sectors [3]. Many manufacturing firms are still new to the concept of lean manufacturing due to insufficient information systems, a lack of formal training, financial resources, cooperation, and mutual trust between management and employees [4, 5]. The literature review focused on the critical success factors and performance measures of lean implementation, as well as the challenges faced during implementation. Several similarities were found among various researchers despite differences in terminologies used. However, the underlying meaning was the same. Surveys in various countries concerning the success of lean implementation, the critical success factors, and the barriers have been reported, which indicates appendix I. Suárez-Barraza, M. F. and Ramis-Pujol, J.[43], surveyed in Mexico on providing a successful example of how lean is adopted Lean enablers: commitment to and wish for improvement, clear resolve to improve, focus on the simple and practical, active leadership, The service is outcome/customer/stakeholder-oriented, holistic and transversal thinking and creating a performance measurements system. Lean inhibitors: Resistance to change by employees, a lack of training, classical bureaucratic mode, organizational structure, creating small freedom, The influence of trade unions with

little interest in change, A lack of credibility in certain middle management, and lack of a strong link between lean efforts and the HRM best practices required to consolidate them.

Achanga, P., et. al.[89], in the UK, identified four lean critical success factors required for lean in SMEs leadership & management, financial capabilities, skills and expertise, and organizational culture.

Motwani, J., [90], explored in the USA the critical factors involved in the implementation of lean process success factors change requires the strategic initiative of top management acting as a leader in defining and communicating the vision of change, willingness to learn, culture readiness, and knowledge sharing.

Bakås, O., et.al [91], address the challenges they face in EU SMEs and identify the success factors. suggested strong critical success factors were strong leadership and management involvement, employee involvement and participation, sufficient time to prepare, organization and cultural change, creating motivation and learning, communication of lean goals and objectives, performance evaluation system, and linking lean to business strategy and customers.

Roslin, E. N., et al.[92], reported in Malaysia on a successful lean initiative taken by a manufacturing firm and discussed the factors that led to that success. The lean adoption process is a top-down holistic approach. Adaptation to lean is a knowledge-intensive process, hence top management is required to have a clear vision and strategic initiatives, and a sufficient level of education & training. Therefore, the lean success factors were top management support & continuous commitment, organizational and cultural change, motivated and empowered employees, involving people a teamwork is the heart of the lean organization, Investing in lean activities, and focusing on long-term benefits and financial capability. Further, the barriers to lean were investigated such as lack of leanness understanding (the conceptual idea of lean and its application and tools), resistance to change, and lack of financial resources.

Laureani, A. and Antony, J.,[93], identify in different EU countries the critical success factors for adopting lean manufacturing the most vital factors are management commitment, cultural change, linking lean to business strategy, and leadership styles.

Dora, M. K., et al.[94], exploring in Belgium the effect of lean manufacturing successful factors. Determining factors of lean manufacturing adoption process exploring top management commitment, organizational culture, the culture of teamwork, and skilled workforce.

Karim, M. A., et al.[95], investigating Saudi Arabia's lean implementation level in manufacturing companies Barriers to lean manufacturing implementation were organizational culture, lack of management commitment, and lack of skilled workers.

Kumar, M.et al. [96], investigating in the UK the quality initiatives practiced by UK manufacturing SEMs. Comparing these practices in Six Sigma firms and its Non-Six Sigma counterparts. The benefits of lean. The key pre-requisite factors facilitating lean adoption were explored Lean sustainability: measuring the commitment to lean culture, treating lean as a profitable initiative, and a strategy of embracing lean. Furthermore, investigating the lean critical success factors are management involvement and commitment, communication, leadership skills, link lean to the employee, culture change, education, and training, link lean to the customer, project selection, link lean to the supplier, project management skill, organization infrastructure, vision and plan, availability of resources and link lean to strategic organization objectives. In addition, the researchers are exploring the barriers to lean are lack of knowledge and training, internal resistance, poor employee participation, and changing business focus.

Bhasin, S. [97], explored the manufacturing sector in the UK and carried out the importance of an appropriate systematic change strategy leading to the probability of successful lean adoption. Discussing the significance of embracing lean as an ideology that allows companies to obtain the full benefits of lean suggested that an extensive audit with companies showed the importance of a systematic and well-planned change strategy for embracing lean initiative. A strategy in which a company communicates what objectives are to be sought and how these objectives will be achieved. Furthermore, the researchers investigated the factors the barriers to lean implementations are inadequate understanding of the potential

benefits, insufficient funding, senior management skills, supervisory skills, lack of skilled workforce, the cost of the investment, and organizational culture issues. Since, the key pre-requisite factors facilitating lean adoption to lean sustainability are measuring the commitment to lean culture, treating lean as a profitability initiative, and a strategy of embracing lean. The lean critical success factors, implementation of lean, and barriers were investigated by various researchers who attempted to research in various countries and sectors of SMEs. Lean success factors, lean implementation, and lean barriers in SMEs implementing without prior knowledge of lean are unsuccessful attempts. Therefore, the role of each success factor and lean barriers are significant during lean implementation.

However, in the few studies found about failing implementations, the common root causes are related to management commitment and support, leadership; employee involvement; financial capability, working culture, human resource management, tools and techniques; and business systems. The barriers in the critical success factors implementation of lean manufacturing can be linked to management, lack of necessary resources, resistance to change, etc. Management can be both a barrier but also a driver for lean implementation. When considering management as a barrier, this is related to specific attitudes and behaviours such as exerting a lack of focus for supporting lean manufacturing initiatives, absence of knowledge on lean philosophy, lack of implementation practice results, and resistance to change by the employees, are a common barriers and into confusion about lean. The study of surveys in other countries allowed for the identification of agreements, investigation of essential lean practices, success factors, and barriers, and selection of the questionnaire for this research. Moreover, based on the review of the literature the researcher investigated how related the critical success factors in the context of lean manufacturing. The critical success factors (CSFs) are the vital ingredients of the LM and the processes that can be controlled by the management to meet the company's aims and objectives. In the context of lean manufacturing - CSFs - this implies if the conditions associated with the factors are not achieved; then sustainable lean manufacturing implementation has less chance of becoming a reality [6]. Therefore, identifying factors that explain the lean manufacturing adoption process is a priority for organizations planning to embark on the development of lean manufacturing [7]. Therefore, to benefit from lean initiatives, companies must understand lean critical success factors and the risks associated with lean implementation and take action to mitigate those risks. [8].

According to Antosz and Stadnicka [9], studies found failing implementations, the common root causes are related to management commitment and support, leadership; employee involvement; financial capability, working culture, human resource management, tools, and techniques; and business systems. The barriers to the implementation of lean manufacturing can be linked to management, lack of necessary resources, resistance to change, etc. Management can be both a barrier but also a driver for lean implementation. When considering management as a barrier, this is related to specific attitudes and behaviors such as exerting a lack of focus for supporting lean manufacturing initiatives, absence of knowledge on lean philosophy, lack of implementation practice results, resistance to change by the employees, a common barrier and into confusion about lean confirmed the barriers in lean implementation to CSFs. Moreover, it considers the surveys in various countries about the success of lean implementation and the critical success factors that were implemented. After reviewing the literature, it can be concluded that the CSFs and performance measures of lean manufacturing are essential elements that can significantly improve an organization's profitability and operational performance. Furthermore, lean manufacturing remains a philosophy that is recognized worldwide to the elimination of wastes in processes to increase the production capacity, while reducing costs and production cycle time. According to Jaiswal and Kumar [10], the UK, Australia, and the USA experienced significant benefits by adopting lean manufacturing techniques in the construction sector.

Despite the benefits that lean manufacturing can offer to organizations, there have been several implementation failures and difficulties attributable to various lean implementation barriers. These barriers include a lack of comprehensive lean methodology, a weak quality policy, and the risk of sustainable

practices implementation [1]. Before implementing lean manufacturing, the industry must understand and address the factors that influence its success and failure. This will allow them to focus their efforts on filling the gaps and reducing the chance of failure. Previous research pointed out that lean manufacturing and implementing lean tools and practices were focused on manufacturing products, which was ignoring the fundamental elements behind the success of these tools, such as human resource management, top management, leadership, financial capability, customer focus, and organizational culture. Lean Manufacturing (LM) is a well-known concept throughout the manufacturing industry that can assist organizations in ways that go far beyond simple cost-cutting. Lean manufacturing can increase an organization's efficiency, produce high-quality products, reduce waste, and decrease costs [11]. Most companies have increasingly come to understand the lean concept's strategic value and the potential for achieving a competitive advantage through lean implementation. Due to the shifting business environment, intense rivalry, continually evolving technology, and increasing customer demand, manufacturers and service providers face cost-cutting and quality improvement problems [12]. The lean mindset encourages companies to prioritize waste reduction, value-stream optimization, and customer satisfaction to produce high-quality products and services over time [13-17]. According to an empirical study, implementing lean has a significant strategic impact on a quality control system, producing products that quickly generate little to no waste, and improve performance and competitiveness [12]. The effectiveness of every quality management innovation is defined by a company's ability to implement it successfully and efficiently. However, implementing lean is a difficult and time-consuming process, and its advantages are not simply acquired [12, 16]. Several researchers have expressed logical concerns. Because of these performance problems, a research agenda has been formed to explore the primary success elements that influence the effectiveness of lean practice deployments. At this point, the ability to assess critical success criteria was necessary to regulate the implementation process and increase the likelihood of success [18-20]. Previous research revealed the potential of several critical success factors (CSFs) [21-24]. The crucial success factors are universally relevant and implemented by companies of any size. However, significant difficulties in identifying and selecting acceptable important variables are due to a lack of consensus over a complete framework or certain criteria. In addition, the area of CSF is broad research and opaque requiring comprehensive work that organizes earlier studies on the development of the lean concept and provides an overview of a common ground for practice and academics. Manufacturing export trade performance and the role of the economy in Ethiopia's metal industry have a lower export performance of 8% and a gross domestic product (GDP) contribution of 0.40% [25]. Despite this, the industry contributions to GDP such as productivity, financial performance, and global competitiveness caused cost-related issues to corporate sustainability were low and inexperience [26]. Ethiopia's steel and iron sectors were also in their infancy with a low market share of GDP contributions [27, 28]. This is because most local industries have low technological capabilities, inadequate resource utilization, limited, ineffective continuous improvement programs, and infrastructure issues [29]. However, the extent of lean implementation practice in Ethiopia has yet to be examined. Despite using technology, there is still a scarcity of knowledge on the use of LM which has encouraged the initiation of this research. From a long-term global viewpoint, a successful strategy is the best and the way to increase LM. However, there is a misunderstanding of the connection between lean critical success factors and performance measurements among experts in the industry. Many of the previous studies discussed that CSFs apply to all types of businesses. Few researchers have focused on the performance and supply chain effects, of Ethiopia's basic metal industry. Additionally, a demand and supply chain analysis of the basic metal industry in Ethiopia has been conducted [30]. Furthermore, total quality management, supply chain, and just-in-time were examined to enhance the global competitiveness of basic metal industries [31]. In addition, how the lean philosophy could raise the competitiveness of Ethiopian chemical industries on a global scale was investigated by Jilch K. et.al [32]. The present work illustrates the various impacts of implementing lean manufacturing in Ethiopia's context along with the priority of the task to be performed for competitive

advantage and sustainability in the global market. Therefore, this case study focused on critical success factors and performance measures of lean implementation in the industry of contemporary events. The study aimed to answer how the industry analyses critical success factors and performance measures of lean implementation. Why did the industry fail to implement these factors? For this study, to address these questions, the case study method was selected.

A survey questionnaire was collected from the literature review of the related topic and distributed to the industry employees. The data were analysed statistically the results were presented and discussed.

Based on the findings of the previous studies, this study constructed a research model that developed seven lean critical success factor components including 19 measurable variables such as leadership, human resource management, customer focus, financial capabilities, organizational culture, top management commitment, and performance measurements of lean manufacturing concerns was emphasized. Therefore, the proposed research model was empirically investigated, and the relationship between lean critical success factors and lean operational performance covariance-based structural equation modelling (CB-SEM) was analysed using the analysis of moment of structures (AMOS). Many CSFs, which had been discussed in the previous literature are generic for all types of organizations. However, they may exert different degrees of impact on SMEs depending on the company and industry. Therefore, proper identification of the main CSFs is essential to increase the chance of success in LM adoption for the ABMI. However, this research was not previously studied in the ABMI and was distinctive. Therefore, it will be a new contribution to enhance industry productivity, profitability, and growth. This study will help the management or lean practitioners of the Akaki basic metal industry to prioritize predominant CSFs so that the management and policymakers can work on a suitable improvement strategy to move forward and become more sustainable in lean manufacturing. The structure of the paper has been designed in the following order: section 1 introduces lean manufacturing practices in the ABMI, research gaps, and its contributions, Section 2 discusses the methodology, Section 3 the result and discussion presented, and Section 4 concludes with the implication of the study.

Literature Review

Reviewing the literature revealed that although lean practices have already been applied in many developing countries, the level of understanding of its underlined philosophy varies. Recent research on lean manufacturing literature revealed that only 14% of studies were conducted in developing countries whereas 86% were conducted in developed Western countries [33]. The organizational culture is the most important driver for creating strategies to achieve the company's objectives [34]. Thus, an organization's culture can have a positive or negative effect on the organization's lean efforts [35, 36]. Before taking the initiative to adopt lean manufacturing, the company is required to change its culture and the way its employees behave [37, 38]. The company's culture and change management are considered an underlying cause behind every lean manufacturing failure [39, 40]. The factors such as values, beliefs, and ideologies that affect the behaviours and practices of the workers in an organization are very important in lean implementation [41]. The top management commitment has been widely considered as a vital factor that could be demonstrated in the form of developing a clear vision ensuring sufficient financial resources, and providing strategic leadership [42, 43]. The empirical evidence indicated that management commitment and support affected negatively and positively the efforts of implementing lean initiatives [44]. Lean manufacturing success is usually the implementation team leader who sets up and chairs the lean change steering committee to ensure best practice is transferred across all functions. The implementation of a lean manufacturing initiative needs support at the grass-roots level in the organization, and it becomes mandatory for lean success to make the organization aware of the importance of lean at all levels [40]. Therefore, for developing countries to transform lean successfully, they need to consider certain factors that well-industrialized developed countries have done, which most researchers have recommended.

Critical success factors (CSFs) are important factors that have significant effects on the performance of a competitive manufacturing organization. Top management involvement and commitment, organizational

culture, training and education, leadership, and customer focus are critical factors for the implementation of quality improvement initiatives [12]. Therefore, to achieve the expected success and benefit of lean implementation top management involvement, commitment and employees must understand the LM concept [45, 46]. Thus, the success of Lean Manufacturing depends on the Leadership must take the necessary measures to ensure that the organization achieves efficient progress and improvement [47, 48]. Näslund [49], argues that CSFs are more closely related to how an organization controls certain components of change activities than to the change approaches themselves. Yadav, V.et al. [45], demonstrate that a lack of lean awareness and limited knowledge were the challenges of the CSFs of lean implementation. According to Netland [50], the level of lean implementation increases the value of success factors with the highest leadership ranking of lean implementation. The accomplishment of lean manufacturing depends upon top management commitments, training, and educating the workers to implement lean production, increase their experience, and make decisions. To achieve the expected success in lean implementation provide the necessary resources and employees must understand and execute lean manufacturing practices [46]. Some researchers have utilized techniques such as fuzzy AHP and analytic hierarchy processes to model the critical success factors (CSFs) involved in implementing lean practices [47, 48]. Ahmad et al. [51] observed the similarities and differences in critical success factors (CSFs) between ERP and lean tools. However, Achanga et al. [52] created a lean system based on fuzzy logic. Van Landeghem [53] and Rose et al. [54], explored the potential of lean implementations to achieve sustainability focused on lean practices. Rymaszewska [55], utilized a benchmark strategy. Some researchers developed a model of lean implementation CSFs for organizational improvement by using DEMATEL, fuzzy DEMATEL, fuzzy Delphi, AHP, and fuzzy AHP methods [56-60]. Most of the researchers confirmed that management involvement and commitment, customer satisfaction, good leadership, cultural change, employee satisfaction, employee empowerment, linking to suppliers, and management skills, knowledge, financial capability, and learning skills play a significant role in the CSFs are necessary for successful lean implementation. However, this research work has developed a new model of analysis of lean critical success factors, and the performance measure of lean implementation CB-SEM using AMOS modeling. Thus, based on the above literature, the present research poses the following objectives:

- (i) Identify the various CSFs of lean implementation and the opinion of industry experts;
- (ii) Draw graphical model and interpret SEM;
- (iii) Analyze the relationship of SEM using AMOS for prediction and results.

II. MODEL DEVELOPMENT AND HYPOTHESES

The model was developed for the influence of CSFs in the context of the ABMI scenario. Therefore, to fill the gap in the literature, AMOS was employed to analyze the SEM, path analysis, and confirmatory analysis. This can draw models graphically and quickly perform the results as shown in Figure 1. For the above discussion, the following hypotheses were proposed:

- H1. Leadership is positively related to the performance measure of lean manufacturing;
- H2. Customer focus is positively related to the performance measure of lean manufacturing;
- H3. Human resource management is positively related to the performance measure of lean manufacturing;
- H4. Financial capability is positively related to the performance measure of lean manufacturing;
- H5. Top management commitment is positively related to the performance measure of lean manufacturing;
- H6. Organizational culture is positively related to the performance measure of lean manufacturing.

Fig. 1. Hypotheses Model and Research

III. DEMOGRAPHICS

This study was focused on the Akaki basic metal industry which manufactures hand tools and equipment in Ethiopia. It has more than 250 employees. The survey was conducted on employees such as supervisors, production heads, engineers, and managers with experience in the manufacturing industry. The questionnaire contains a total of 7 constructs and 31 questions. A total of 240 surveys were distributed and received feedback from 220 respondents, which demonstrates that the rate of responses was a value of 91.6%. Based on the demographic data the following responses were collected. The position with the largest participation a value of 47%, was in the quality department. The male participation was higher a value of 87%. 75% of the highest age participants were from 26-46 years. The participants' responses had a value of 75% which was no lean awareness. The source of lean awareness was a value of 55% response rate in the quality department. The employee's educational level with a diploma was 47.3% which was higher than the other qualifications. 34.1% of the total participants responded that the benefits of implementing lean for productivity improvement were significant. A value of 34.5% of the participants responded that the challenge of lean implementation was a lack of knowledge. In contrast, 56.4% of those surveyed had fewer than 10 years of experience as shown in Appendix II.

The previous research confirmed that the lean implementation and adoption process was challenging, expensive, and dependent on the organization's culture changing and accepting new working practices at organizational levels [61, 62]. Based on previous research indicated that 10% of the industry applied lean manufacturing principles confirming that the majority of employees had a misunderstanding of the lean concept [63]. These findings supported the assertion that the industry investigation into the failures of misunderstanding the lean concept was reasonable [64].

Table I, indicates the level of lean awareness practices of the response rate of the respondents as 75% had no awareness while 25% of the respondents had awareness.

Table II Shows the source of lean awareness stated by the respondents was 55%, 15%, 15%, 12.3 %, and 2.7 %, in the quality department, top management, consultants, competitors, and marketing, respectively.

Table III shows that the awareness of lean tools stated by the respondents was, 49.1%, 13.6%, 8.2%, 10.9 %, 7.7 %, 6.4%, 2.7%, and 1.4%, about kaizen, total productivity, quality circle, 5S, JIT, standardization followed by Value Stream Mapping respectively.

TABLE I
LEVEL OF AWARENESS OF LEAN PRACTICES

Valid	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	55	25.0	25.0	25.0
No	165	75.0	75.0	100.0
Total	220	100.0	100.0	

TABLE II
SOURCE OF AWARENESS

Valid	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Top Management	33	15.0	15.0	15.0
Consultant	33	15.0	15.0	30.0
Quality Department	121	55.0	55.0	85.0
Marketing	6	2.7	2.7	87.7
Competitor	27	12.3	12.3	100.0
Total	220	100.0	100.0	

TABLE III
AWARENESS OF LEAN TOOLS

Valid	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Kaizen	108	49.1	49.1	49.1
Value Stream Mapping	6	2.7	2.7	51.8
Quality circle	24	10.9	10.9	62.7
Single-Minute Exchange of Die	3	1.4	1.4	64.1
JIT	17	7.7	7.7	71.8
Standardization	14	6.4	6.4	78.2
5S	18	8.2	8.2	86.4
Total productivity maintenance	30	13.6	13.6	100.0
Total	220	100.0	100.0	

Table IV shows the benefits of lean implementation practices declared by the respondents were a value of 34.1% for productivity, 25.9% for on-time delivery, 20.9% for quality improvement, 12.3% for lead time reduction, 5.5% for financial impact, and 1.4% for stock reduction.

TABLE IV
IMPLEMENTATION OF LEAN PRACTICES

Valid	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Productivity improvement	75	34.1	34.1	34.1
On-time delivery	57	25.9	25.9	60.0
Financial impact	12	5.5	5.5	65.5
Stock reduction	3	1.4	1.4	66.8
Lead time reduction	27	12.3	12.3	79.1
Quality improvement	46	20.9	20.9	100.0
Total	220	100.0	100.0	

Table V shows the challenges of lean implementation practices declared by the respondents were a value of 38.8% for lack of capital funds, 34.5% for lack of knowledge, 26.8% for lack of awareness, 9.5% for middle management resistance, 4.1% for not easy to implement and 1.4% for employee resistance.

TABLE V
CHALLENGES OF IMPLEMENTING LEAN PRACTICES

Valid	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Lack of capital fund	43	38.8	19.5	19.5
Not easy to implement	9	4.1	4.1	23.6
Middle Management resistance	21	9.5	9.5	33.2
Employee resistance	3	1.4	1.4	34.5
Lack of knowledge	76	34.5	34.5	69.1
Lack of awareness	59	26.8	26.8	95.9
Lack of time	9	4.1	4.1	100.0
Total	220	100.0	100.0	

IV. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a survey approach-based methodologies to identify a set of critical success factors (CSFs) using a comprehensive review of the literature. The survey design was used as a methodology for data gathering tools to generate and validate the data [65, 66]. The lean implementation has not been well-researched in the Ethiopia context, particularly in the ABMI. This study identified the lean implementation CSFs and performance measures of lean through a literature review and industry expert opinion. Further, it relates the identified CSFs and performance measures of lean using EFA, CFA, AMOS, and CB-SEM techniques were analyzed. These techniques were constructed in groups based on factor loading, and the reliability and validity of the constructs were confirmed. The research methodology was used in nine different phases, as depicted in Figure 2.

Phase 1. Instrument design

The instrument was developed based on the literature review and industry experts' opinion which helped to identify the lean implementation CSFs in the ABMI. A literature review was conducted using various databases including Springer, Google Scholar, Elsevier, and IEEE.

Phase 2. Questionnaire administration

The questionnaire consisted of two sections; the first was based on the general information of the respondent, whereas the second was the selection of lean implementations CSFs and performance measures of lean as shown in Appendix II and Appendix III. A five-point Likert scale questionnaire was prepared. The questionnaire displayed preferences for respondents' feedback, as strongly disagree, disagree, neutral, agree, and strongly agree which were represented by 1,2,3,4 and 5, respectively. The pilot testing of the questionnaire was reviewed by industry experts, academics, and lean manufacturing consultants which was discussed in detail to ensure the content's validity, readability, and brevity. This informed the researcher of any potential difficulties that resulted from the questionnaire design. The pilot test was a revised instrument before examining the relationship between variables to maintain consistency and eliminate the need for rework. This research study examined the measurement scales such as whether any questions should be included or excluded; whether the instrument's content was sufficient; whether the appropriate questions were being posed, and its clarity to comprehend. Participants' feedback was used to improve the instrument's clarity, and language, and some measuring items were added, removed, or adjusted. Thus, it was critical to investigate model fitness, reliability, and validity before examining the link between variables [67, 68]. To ensure adherence to the university declaration, the internal review board approved the study. Participants completed a consent form after a brief presentation, agreed to participate in the study, and indicated their option to leave at any time. Further, they were permitted to refuse to answer any questions. It was agreed upon the confidential use of collected data, with no direct benefit from participation. Participants agreed to the interview, unidentified identity, and the ability to retain the original data with the researcher. They were further permitted to access collected data at any time, with full freedom to contact any participant.

Phase 3. Statistical analysis for questionnaire validation

Tests were conducted to validate the questionnaire's reliability and the validity of indirectly observed variables and assess using factor analysis [69]. The factor analysis verified the outliers, missing data, multicollinearity, and assumptions of univariate and multivariate normality. The data were entered into the database to find outliers observations with unusual characteristics [70, 71]. The surveys met the standard level of statistical significance $P < 0.001$ as recommended by Kline [72]. However, the survey validation was taken into account by 220 responses. Principal component analysis using maximum likelihood approaches was used to extract the factor cross-loading to improve the database normality as reported under this assumption [73]. The skewness and kurtosis tests were also utilized to verify the multivariate normality of variables described by De Carlo, [74]. The results indicated that the values of skewness and kurtosis were less than 3, which confirmed that the data were valid for the analysis as indicated in Table VI. The Mardia was used as a statistical test to determine multivariate normality based on the normalized value of multivariate kurtosis, where statistical tests were used to determine the normalized Kurtosis value of multivariate normality [75]. The procedure involves comparing the Mardia coefficient with a calculated value obtained from the formula $p(p + 2)$ [69]. This assumption was validated by comparing the multivariate kurtosis calculated using the recommended formula to obtain the value using SPSS Amos graphics. The redundancy of items was found that the model fitness did not fit. To address these issues, covariance was used as an indicator or error terms as a free parameter, and then deleted the duplicated items [67]. The remaining 19 items were considered for the analysis as shown in Table VI. The result indicated that $19 \times (19 + 2)$ the value of 399 calculated from the data was higher than the multivariate kurtosis index of 220.533. This was determined through analysis using the statistical software SPSS Amos 23.0 which confirmed multivariate normality met the data sets for the analysis [76].

TABLE VI
ASSESSMENT OF NORMALITY

Variable	Min	Max	Skew	C.R.	Kurtosis	C.R.
PML4	1.000	5.000	0.076	0.460	-1.249	-3.781
PML3	1.000	5.000	-0.123	-0.746	-1.220	-3.693
OC1	1.000	4.000	0.937	5.672	-0.634	-1.920
OC2	1.000	5.000	0.950	5.754	-0.290	-0.879
OC4	1.000	5.000	0.909	5.502	-0.386	-1.168
TMC2	1.000	5.000	1.177	7.129	0.515	1.561
TMC3	1.000	5.000	1.194	7.232	0.510	1.543
TMC4	1.000	4.000	1.152	6.974	0.423	1.280
FC1	1.000	5.000	1.409	8.529	0.746	2.258
FC2	1.000	5.000	1.169	7.080	0.368	1.113
HRM1	1.000	5.000	0.731	4.424	-0.251	-0.758
HRM2	1.000	5.000	0.855	5.179	0.054	0.164
HRM4	1.000	5.000	0.842	5.097	0.013	0.040
CF1	1.000	5.000	0.339	2.055	-0.920	-2.785
CF2	1.000	5.000	0.343	2.080	-0.964	-2.919
CF3	1.000	5.000	0.528	3.198	-0.497	-1.506
LS5	1.000	5.000	0.614	3.719	-0.515	-1.559
LS7	1.000	5.000	0.506	3.062	-1.036	-3.136
LS8	1.000	5.000	0.629	3.812	-0.677	-2.050
Multivariate					20.533	57.897

Phase 4. Data collection

The data for this research was obtained from the Akaki Basic Metal Industry (ABMI), Ethiopia which was surveyed from 20/10/22 to 15/8/2023. The survey was designed to the analysis of lean critical success

factors and performance measures of lean using CB-SEM. A brief introduction of the research objectives was highlighted at the beginning of the questionnaire. The questionnaire was filled out by engineers and managers who were connected to the production line. A total of 240 questionnaires were distributed via personal visits to ABMI; 220 valid responses were received. Thus giving an acceptable response rate of 91.6 % is sufficient as per Nulty, D.D. [77].

Phase 5. Sampling

Sample adequacy was examined by Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) using SPSS AMOS 23 software. The results indicated a value of $0.783 > 0.5$. This confirmed that the sample size in this study was sufficient for EFA based on the KMO value obtained [78]. This was performed to provide a clear understanding of the considerable level of sample adequacy that was analyzed as indicated in Table VII.

Phase 6. Variables and Measures

This study employed a 5-point Likert scale to quantify the research variables, a methodological choice to capture the degree of respondents' attitudes or emotional responses towards specific issues. The measurement system where a score of 1 signifies "strongly disagree", while a score of 5 represents "strongly agree". This scale was a popular alternative for measuring latent variables in operations management studies as supported [79, 80]. This scaling approach effectively transforms attitudinal concepts into quantifiable metrics. The tangible numerical values were analyzed through EFA, CFA, and AMOS. This ensures a robust and interpretable dataset that gives a comprehensive analysis, thereby adding empirical rigor to this study [81]. The constructs of CSFs were measured including leadership, customer focus, human resource management, performance measures of lean, top management commitment, and organizational culture.

Phase 7. Variable operationalization

Based on the exploratory factor analysis results and experts' opinions 7 CSFs constructed and each construct had more than 4 indicators; only 32 items were selected; 13 items were deleted because of redundancy of the items and cross-loading. The remaining 19 items were chosen and grouped with the factor loading into 7 constructs based on eigenvalues greater than one confirmed as indicated in Table VII. The seven CSF constructs were investigated during the survey. This was the initial step in the process of operationalizing the constructs [82, 83]. Each construct was provided along with an item that was acceptable to the CSFs to be assessed as indicated in Appendix III.

Phase 8. Data analysis

The validity and reliability of the data were checked using Cronbach's Alpha. Kaiser- Meyer-Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett's tests were also performed to provide a clear understanding of the considerable level of sample adequacy before the data were analyzed. Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) was used to describe the variables in a dataset using principal component analysis (PCA), and maximum likelihood (ML) methods for factor reduction, simplification, and interpretation of the factor structure underlying a set of variables.

Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was the measurement approach to evaluate the convergent and discriminant validity of the constructs. CB-SEM was the most appropriate for the analysis of a fundamental theory-driven route model [84].

Phase 9. In the final phase, the structural relationship of regression analysis and the model fitness indices were examined using analysis moment structures (AMOS). This yielded significant research outcomes for the study

Fig. 2. Research Methodology

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

1. Factor Analysis

(i) Exploratory Factor analysis

The component was extracted using PCA techniques for estimation of maximum likelihood and Varimax Kaiser Normalization rotation converged in 7 iteration methods was the most important technique in EFA interpretation [70]. A varimax rotation was used in this investigation because, apart from distributional assumptions, it is likely to produce inaccurate responses that are not associated [85]. Based on the exploratory factor analysis results and experts' opinions 7 CSFs constructed and each construct had more than 4 indicators; 32 items were selected and 13 items were deleted due to redundancy and cross-loading. The remaining 19 items were chosen and grouped with the factor loading into 7 constructs based on eigenvalues greater than one selected. Table VII shows a summary of exploratory factor analysis after rotation sums of squared loading. The EFA permitted the discovery of seven factors, a total of 19 variables with significant loading and explaining a value of 88.138% of the total variation in the data was greater than the minimum acceptable value of variance of 75%, which was valid. Further, the eigenvalues of all of the factors were greater than one, was confirmed that the number of the factor analysis were verified. Since the exploratory factor analysis results indicated that after rotating, the sum of the square factor structure loading relationship indicates, that no cross-loading items remained. Only 19 items were valid for the analysis as shown in Table VII.

Reliability and Validity of the construct

EFA was implemented to assess the validity of all variables using the PCA technique and varimax rotation was used to measure the factor analysis of all structures. Further, Cronbach's alpha was used to measure the internal consistency reliability of the construct. The obtained value of the overall Cronbach's alpha was 0.89, which is higher than 0.70. This indicates the high reliability of the proposed model [72]. Table VII shows the factor loadings for 19 variables which is higher than 0.70. This indicates that they are significant.

(ii) Confirmatory Factor Analysis

SPSS Amos graphics version 23, was used for confirmatory analysis (CFA). Outliers and multicollinearity of the data were sought, as well as univariate and multivariate normality. Any issues with assumptions were eliminated and the sample size of 220 surveys was retained for the tests [73]. The model enhancement was active for improvement at the proposed level which excluded cross-loading factors to get the specified scale levels. The optimal data reliability value was greater than 0.7 [67]. The results show that the factor loading of all the items was more than 0.7, which was consistent with the proposals and is also significant at the confidence level of 5% (Table VIII) [74]. Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) is a powerful method used to assess construct validity, which was convergent and discriminant validity were examined as shown in Table VIII and Table IX. Model fitness refers to the model's ability to reproduce the existing linkage with other data tested under similar conditions. A well-fitted model ensures consistency and prevents reworking. Thus, it is essential to examine model fitness after reliability and validity were proven before assessing the linkage between variables. Using the factor loadings, error variance, and Cronbach alpha value, the composite reliability, convergent validity, and internal consistency of the model were valid as shown in Tables VIII and IX.

Convergent Validity

The AVE was used to assess convergent validity for a value greater than 0.5 indicates good convergent validity [71]. Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability ranged from 0.881 to 0.89 and 0.725 to 0.984, respectively. These values were more than the threshold value of 0.7 which indicates that the questionnaire and its components were reliable and valid [86] as shown in Table VIII.

TABLE VII

SUMMARY OF EXPLORATORY FACTOR ANALYSIS AFTER ROTATION SUMS OF SQUARED LOADING

Construct	Items	Factors						
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Top Management Commitment	TMC2	0.926						
	TMC3	0.919						
	TMC4	0.902						
Organizational Culture	OC1		0.926					
	OC2		0.926					
	OC4		0.913					
Customer Focus	CF1			0.869				
	CF2			0.892				
	CF3			0.894				
Leadership Commitment	LS5				0.861			
	LS7				0.895			
	LS8				0.893			
Human Resource Management	HRM1					0.873		
	HRM2					0.9		
	HRM4					0.873		
Financial Capability	FC1 FC2						0.922 0.942	
Performance Measure of Lean Manufacturing	PML3							0.869
	PML4							0.822
Eigenvalues		2.96	2.906	2.796	2.771	2.708	1.854	1.631
Percent of Variance explained		14.802	14.531	13.982	13.857	13.542	9.269	8.155
Cumulative variance		14.802	29.332	43.315	57.172	70.714	79.983	88.138
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy	0.783							
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity								
Approx. Chi-Square	4969.125							
df	190							
Sig.	0							
Overall Cronbach's Alpha	0.89							

TABLE VIII

RELIABILITY AND VALIDITY TEST

Factors	No of items	Deleted of items	Factor loading	CR	AVE	Cronbach's alpha	Overall Cronbach's alpha
LS5	3	5	0.861	0.952	0.87	0.881	0.89
LS7			0.895			0.882	
LS8			0.893			0.881	
CF1	3	1	0.869	0.954	0.875	0.881	
CF2			0.892			0.882	
CF3			0.894			0.883	
HRM1	3	1	0.873	0.928	0.811	0.883	
HRM2			0.9			0.883	
HRM4			0.873			0.885	
PML3	2	2	0.869	0.726	0.572	0.89	
PML4			0.822			0.888	
FC1	2	2	0.922	0.919	0.851	0.889	
FC2			0.942			0.89	
TMC2	3	1	0.926	0.984	0.953	0.884	
TMC3			0.919			0.884	
TMC4			0.902			0.884	
OC1	3	1	0.926	0.976	0.93	0.886	
OC2			0.926			0.885	
OC4			0.913			0.885	

Discriminant Validity

Discriminant validity determines how distinct one construct is from the others. The diagonal square root of AVE for each construct was greater than the variance shared between the construct and other constructs in the model as indicated in Table IX. The results satisfied the discriminant validity.

TABLE IX
DISCRIMINANT VALIDITY

Coding	CR	AVE	MSV	ASV	PML.	LS.	CF.	HRM.	FC.	TMC.	OC.
PML.	0.726	0.572	0.174	0.084	0.756						
LS.	0.952	0.870	0.383	0.121	0.190	0.933					
CF.	0.954	0.875	0.383	0.117	0.202	0.619	0.935				
HRM.	0.928	0.811	0.228	0.103	0.225	0.478	0.477	0.901			
FC.	0.919	0.851	0.174	0.052	0.417	0.146	0.094	0.254	0.922		
TMC.	0.984	0.953	0.358	0.100	0.367	0.192	0.129	0.200	0.115	0.976	
OC.	0.976	0.930	0.358	0.083	0.262	0.134	0.152	0.070	0.165	0.598	0.964

2. Measurement Model

The measurement model validity was evaluated using content validity, internal consistency, convergent validity, and discriminant validity. Furthermore, the content validity of the model fit indices was examined by CB-SEM using AMOS as follows:

2.1. Absolute fit measure

AMOS produces highly complex outputs, either graphically or numerically. Figure 3 and Table X fulfill all the criteria of the measurement model in terms of graphically and numerically. The chi-squared/ degree of freedom (CMIN/DF) value was 2.234 which lies between the 2-5 range which implies a good fit. The RMSEA value was 0.075, located between $0.05 < 0.075 \leq 0.1$ which indicates an acceptable fit [87]. The AMOS computes the value of the SRMR was 0.0334 which lies between $0 \leq 0.034 \leq 0.05$ which indicates the model is a perfect fit [68, 88].

2.2. Incremental fit measure

In this research finding, the Normal Fit Index (NFI) value was 0.943 which lies between $0.90 \leq 0.943 < 0.95$ which indicates an acceptable fit [87]. The Comparative Fit Index (CFI) value was 0.967 and lies between $0.95 \leq 0.967 < 0.97$ indicating an acceptable fit. In addition, the Tucker-Lewis index (TLI) was checked and the path coefficient in the context of AMOS was evaluated. The TLI value of 0.957 lies between $0.95 \leq 0.957 \leq 1.00$ this confirmed a perfect fit of the finding. The value of the Incremental Fit Index (IFI) was 0.967 which lies between $0.95 \leq 0.967 \leq 1.00$ which indicates a perfect fit [67, 87]. Furthermore, the Relative Fit Index (RFI) was truncated in AMOS graphics value of 0.925 which indicated an acceptable fit lies between $0.90 \leq 0.925 < 0.95$ [87].

2.3. Parsimonious fit measure

The Parsimonious Comparative Fit Index (PCFI) and Parsimonious Normal Fit Index (PNFI) generated through AMOS were 0.741 and $0.722 > 0.50$, respectively, indicating that the model was an acceptable fit [88].

TABLE X

CB-CFA MEASUREMENT MODEL FIT SUMMARY

Fit Index	Perfect Fit	Acceptable Fit	Result	Model fit verification
Absolute fit measure		$p < 0.001$	0.000	Significant
CMIN/Df		< 5	2.234	Accepted
RMSEA	$0 \leq RMSEA \leq 0.05$	$0.05 < RMSEA \leq 0.10$	0.075	Accepted
SRMR	$0 \leq SRMR \leq 0.05$	$0.05 < SRMR \leq 0.10$	0.0334	Perfect fit
Incremental fit measure				
NFI	$0.95 \leq NFI \leq 1.00$	$0.90 \leq NFI < 0.95$	0.943	Accepted
CFI	$0.97 \leq CFI \leq 1.00$	$0.95 \leq CFI < 0.97$	0.967	Accepted
TLI	$0.95 \leq TLI \leq 1.00$	$0.90 \leq TLI < 0.95$	0.957	Perfect
IFI	$0.95 \leq IFI \leq 1.00$	$0.90 \leq IFI < 0.95$	0.967	Perfect
RFI	$0.95 \leq RFI \leq 1.00$	$0.90 \leq RFI < 0.95$	0.925	Accepted
Parsimonious fit measure				
PCFI		> 0.50	0.741	Accepted
PNFI		> 0.50	0.722	Accepted

Fig.3. Proposed Measurement Model for LM, CSF with CB-SEM

3. Structural Equation Model (SEM)

SEM was used for data analysis to evaluate causal links between constructs and handle complex models using robust statistical approaches. This permits researchers to examine the interactions between some dependent and independent factors simultaneously. The CB-SEM model was examined by AMOS version 23 in utilizing maximum likelihood (ML) estimation approaches as shown in Figure 4. The CB-SEM model fit summary indicated the value of CMIN/Df was $2.234 < 5$, Root mean standard error approximation(RMSEA) values of $0.075 < 0.10$, and Standard root mean residual(SRMR) values of $0.027 < 0.05$. This indicated that the values confirmed the absolute fitness, Incremental fitness measurement

results of NFI, CFI, TLI, IFI, and RFI were 0.943, 0.967, 0.957, 0.967, and 0.925 > 0.9, respectively. This confirmed that the model was an acceptable fit. PCFI and PNFI values for parsimonious fitness were 0.766 and 0.760 > 0.50, respectively, indicating an acceptable fit. The model with an absolute, incremental, and parsimonious fit was used for hypotheses testing because it meets the criteria for an acceptable fit [67, 87, and 88] as shown in Table XI.

TABLE XI
CB-SEM MODEL FIT SUMMARY

Fit Index	Perfect Fit	Acceptable Fit	Result	Model fit verification
Absolute fit measure		$p < 0.001$	0.000	Significant
CMIN/Df		<5	2.234	Accepted
RMSEA	$0 \leq RMSEA \leq 0.05$	$0.05 < RMSEA \leq 0.10$	0.075	Accepted
SRMR	$0 \leq SRMR \leq 0.05$	$0.05 < SRMR \leq 0.10$	0.027	Perfect fit
Incremental fit measure				
NFI	$0.95 \leq NFI \leq 1.00$	$0.90 \leq NFI < 0.95$	0.943	Accepted
CFI	$0.97 \leq CFI \leq 1.00$	$0.95 \leq CFI < 0.97$	0.967	Accepted
TLI	$0.95 \leq TLI \leq 1.00$	$0.90 \leq TLI < 0.95$	0.957	Accepted
IFI	$0.95 \leq IFI \leq 1.00$	$0.90 \leq IFI < 0.95$	0.967	Accepted
RFI	$0.95 \leq RFI \leq 1.00$	$0.90 \leq RFI < 0.95$	0.925	Accepted
Parsimonious fit measure				
PCFI		>0.50	0.766	Accepted
PNFI		>0.50	0.760	Accepted

Fig. 4. Structural Equation Modelling using CB-SEM

3.1. Hypotheses testing

The AMOS-SEM model was used to evaluate the reliability and validity of the model fitness which were linked between variables. The results confirmed that the model was reliable and valid which indicates an acceptable fit as shown in Table XII. The hypothesis test was performed after verification of the results confirmed that financial capability (FC) and top management commitment were significant as shown in Table XII. H4 referred to FC as having a significant and positive relation between PML and FC. The value of the estimation coefficient of 0.394, standard regression coef, of 0.367, and $P < 0.001$ strongly supported this hypothesis. H5 presumed TMC was a significant and positive relation between PLM and TMC. The value of the estimation coefficient of 0.298, standard regression coef, of 0.309, and $P < 0.001$ strongly supported this hypothesis. The coefficient of determination (R^2) values which quantify how much of an endogenous construct was explained by its predictor, which were utilized as the evaluation criterion confirmed the AMOS-SEM reliability and validity results. The R^2 value indicated that the number of variations of independent variables which were accounted for the results of AMOS-SEM model fitness. A greater R^2 value increases the structural model's predictive capability. As shown in Table XII, the R^2 value was found to be 0.293, indicating that the performance measure of lean (PML) improved the critical success factors of lean at a rate of 29.30%.

TABLE XII
HYPOTHESIS TESTING CB-SEM AFTER THE FIT MODEL

Hypothesis	Relationship			Estimate Coef.	Standardized Regression Coef.	S.E.	C.R.	P	Decision
H1	PML.	<---	LS.	-0.006	-0.007	0.079	-0.072	0.943	NS
H2	PML.	<---	CF.	0.114	0.125	0.088	1.302	0.193	NS
H3	PML.	<---	HRM.	0.014	0.013	0.091	0.152	0.879	NS
H4	PML.	<---	FC.	0.394	0.367	0.082	4.814	***	S
H5	PML.	<---	TMC.	0.298	0.309	0.086	3.442	***	S
H6	PML.	<---	OC.	-0.002	-0.002	0.080	-0.024	0.981	NS
R² PML.= 0.293									

*** Significance level < 0.001, NS= Not supported, S= Supported

TABLE XIII
PATH CORRELATION

Hypothesis	Relationship			Total Effects	Direct Effects	Indirect Effects
H1	PML.	<---	LS.	-0.007	-0.007	0.000
H2	PML.	<---	CF.	0.125	0.125	0.000
H3	PML.	<---	HRM.	0.013	0.013	0.000
H4	PML.	<---	FC.	0.367	0.367	0.000
H5	PML.	<---	TMC.	.0309	0.309	0.000
H6	PML.	<---	OC.	-0.002	-0.002	0.000

Table XIII shows the path correlation of CB-SEM analysis indicating that the top management commitment and financial capability had significant positive and direct effects on the lean manufacturing performance measures a value of 30.9% and 36.7%, respectively. These results were confirmed.

VI. CONCLUSION

The research findings provide evidence to support a research model that specifies the seven most significant dimensions of lean critical success factors and performance measures of lean were analysed through EFA, CFA, and CB-SEM using AMOS. The conclusion of the findings is as follows:

- The percentage of co-variation among items accounted for each component varied before and after rotation and varimax rotation sums squared with Eigenvalues >1 and cumulative variance values ranging from 14.802 to 88.138 %. Thus all items have significant loadings on their respective components.
- The KMO value test has $0.783 > 0.5$ which confirms the sample size of the factor analysis. Whereas Bartlett's test shows $0.000 < 0.001$ this shows the variables' contributing factors were sufficient.
- Confirmatory factor analysis verified the measurement model's convergent validity and discriminant validity were sufficient.
- The findings also demonstrate that top management commitment and financial capability components a value of which together account for 30.9% and 36.7% of the variance have a direct and significant positive effect on the lean manufacturing performance measure, respectively. Therefore, the direct influence of financial capabilities on lean manufacturing performance was greater than top management commitment. The results showed the two hypotheses H4 and H5 were strongly supported.
- The absence of lean essential success factors and performance measures in the Akaki basic metal manufacturing industry has resulted in higher reworks, rejection, defects, customer dissatisfaction, and loss of productivity. As a result, the GDP contribution of Ethiopia's basic metal industry was estimated to be nearly null at 0.4%. Therefore, financial capability and top management's commitment to the lean concept are essential to establishing lean CSFs and achieving industry growth.
- This study concludes that this research will be useful for industry management supported by the concepts and findings to promptly reply to any variation, including changes in production, quality, delivery, and cost considerably improved by the construction of a valid and reliable scale.
- Furthermore, the methodologies are useful to managers in understanding the CSFs of lean implementation, which helps develop strategy and decision-making.

Limitation

This study achieved the objective of the analysis of a relationship between lean critical success factors and performance measures of lean in the ABMI. However, this study only focused on Ethiopia's basic metal industry, particularly ABMI, owing to time, finances, and other constraints. As a result, the generalizability of the results is somewhat constrained. There has been limited research conducted on leanness and related issues in the country and region. Therefore, further investigation is required in this area. Academics and researchers should look into new pathways for high-quality study, both conceptual and empirical to come up with more publications in these fields.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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